

ENVIRONMENTAL OXIDANTS

Villanueva C, Sánchez-González DJ, Moro MA, Castillo-Henkel C, Floriano-Sánchez E, Herrera-González N. Antioxidant Treatment Prevents Effects of Ozone on Nitric Oxide Synthases Expression in Lung. Free Radic Biol Med 2006; 41: (1) S97.

245 Free Radic Biol Med 2006; 41: (1) S97.

Antioxidant Treatment Prevents Effects of Ozone on Nitric Oxide Synthases Expression in Lung

Cleva Villanueva¹, Dolores Javier Sanchez-Gonzalez², Maria Angeles Moro³, Carlos Castillo-Henkel¹, Esau Floriano-Sanchez², and Norma Herrera-Gonzalez¹

¹Escuela Superior de Medicina del IPN, ²Escuela Medico Militar, ³Universidad Complutense de Madrid. Fac. Medicina

Ozone (O₃) exposure modifies the expression of nitric oxide synthases (NOSs) in lungs. Oxidative stress changes NOSs expression in different models. Since O₃ exposure produces oxidative stress, the aim of the study was to investigate if nordihydroguaiaretic acid (NDGA), a potent antioxidant, prevents the effects of O₃ on NOSs expression. Male Wistar rats (10 weeks old) were exposed to O₃ (0.25 ppm, 4 h/day, 7-56 days, control group was kept at 0.05 ppm) in the absence or presence of NDGA (20 mg/kg per day). at the end of the exposure animals were sacrificed and NOSs expression was evaluated by immunohistochemistry (IH) in lung. Lung nitrotyrosine (NT) formation was measured through IH as an evidence of oxidative stress. O₃ increased endothelial (eNOS, from 39.9±1.3 at day 0, to 90.0±2.1 % Area (µm²) at day 56, p<0.001) and inducible (iNOS, from 6.2±0.6 at day 0, to 46.9±0.9 % Area (µm²) at day 56, p<0.001) NOSs, as well as NT formation (from 5.1±0.4 at day 0, to 7.3±0.7 % Area (µm²) at day 56, p=0.03). the neuronal enzyme (nNOS) decreased after O₃ exposure (from 18.7±0.9 at day 0, to 11.1±1.2 % Area (µm²) at day 56, p<0.01). NDGA significantly inhibited changes in iNOS (30.3±1.5 % Area (µm²), at day 56, p<0.0001) and nNOS (33.9±1.1 % Area (µm²) at day 56, p<0.001). NT fell (3.3±0.3 % Area (µm²), at day 56, p=0.0001), while eNOS increased (96.1±1.2 % Area (µm²), at day 56, p=0.03) in O₃ exposed rats treated with NDGA. It is concluded that oxidative stress accounts for changes of iNOS and nNOS, but not of eNOS expression during O₃ exposure.